

**THE IMPORTANCE OF INITIATIVE BUDGETING PRACTICE
IN SOLVING SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROBLEMS IN
NEIGHBORHOODS
(IN THE EXAMPLE OF SURKHONDARYO PROVINCE).**

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ABSTRACT

The article initiative or participatory budgeting institute is considered today as the most important condition for increasing the participation of the population and business in determining the directions of budget spending, and for the development of local self-government. To date, a great deal of experience in initiative budgeting has been accumulated both in Uzbekistan and in foreign countries. Taking into account the historical characteristics and specific features of the tasks facing a particular region, various mechanisms of this institution are used. The article discusses the specific features of this form of budgeting and the problems it allows to solve.

Key words: budget expenditures, initiative budgeting, population initiatives, local community, collaborative budgeting, strategic planning, citizen participation, civic participation, public participation, effectiveness of budget expenditures.

INTRODUCTION

In the world, in the context of public finance reform, scientific research is being conducted on the effective use of financial resources through proactive budgeting. Ensuring the accuracy of the separation of public and private sector management in the effective use of budget funds, strengthening the role of competent bodies in providing budget funds, expanding public participation, monitoring the achievement of fiscal policy goals, financial information and risks, internal and external controls. Determining the interaction, comprehensible and precise formation of financial information, implementation and implementation of real-time mode in ensuring the openness of financial information, improvement of standards for ensuring the openness of financial policy are among the important directions of research in this regard. is considered

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Systematic literature analysis on "initiative budgeting" was carried out in the study. When appropriate, it should be noted that "initiative budgeting" as a practice, method, system, mechanism, approach is called "initiative budgeting", "initiative budgeting", "participatory

budgeting", "transparent budgeting", "electronic participatory budgeting" in various literature. , "participatory budgeting with citizens", was studied as an "innovative approach".

In international experience, initiative budgeting is known as "Participate" (participatory budgeting). The word "Participate" means "participate" in English. Taking into account the initiatives of citizens, making decisions with their direct participation on the distribution of a part of the budget funds and choosing the directions of spending these funds, as well as the practice of monitoring the implementation of the decisions made, is called an initiative budget.

Initiative budgeting is the practice of allocating a part of the budget funds based on the proposals made by citizens, taking into account their initiatives, and using these allocated funds to finance projects based on socially significant proposals put forward by citizens.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In every developed and developing country, there are strategies aimed at achieving economic development and improving the living standards of the population, and such targeted strategies serve as a basis for systematic development. In order to achieve the planned results, one of the most important factors of efficiency is the correct determination of "Time management" while being able to use the necessary mechanisms. In general, in recent years, conducting mass polls on various issues and fields has become widespread in practice, especially conducting polls with wide involvement of the population through Internet networks is becoming popular.

Surveys vary according to the purpose of conducting and by whom, public surveys are usually conducted through face-to-face meetings (live), websites, mass media, various news portals, messengers and other means. will be held. Also, the main goal of conducting surveys is to identify minor and major deficiencies in various areas and implement comprehensive measures to eliminate existing deficiencies based on the opinion of the population.

Today, within the framework of the "Initiative Budget" processes, the social proposals submitted by citizens are determined by voting and financing of the corresponding winning proposal is being carried out in our country.

Proactive budgeting processes are also one of the interactive methods that provide opportunities for positive solutions to citizens' social problems. gives the opportunity to go. According to the Ministry of Economy and Finance, a total of 49,464 projects related to the improvement of the infrastructure of 9,426 neighborhoods across the country were put forward at the end of the project introduction stage for the 2nd season of the "Initiative Budget" of 2023.

15,140 of the proposals (31%) are related to the repair of internal roads. 14,835 proposals (30%) are focused on neighborhood improvement activities. 6,820 (14%) proposals were received for schools, 3,024 (6%) for kindergartens, and 3,100 (6%) for medical institutions (Figure 4). For information, in the 1st season of 2023, the most school-related projects won.

Figure 1. 2023 2nd season Initiative budget projects in sectors.

In terms of initiative, Surkhandarya region is clearly different from other regions. A total of 12,279 proposals were received from 238 neighborhoods in the province. This is equal to 25% of the total initiatives. For comparison, the 2nd highest indicator in this regard belongs to the city of Tashkent, where residents of the capital submitted 4020 offers to the portal. (Fig. 5)

The people of Surkhandarya have been consistently taking the 1st place in terms of submission of proposals. In the 2nd season of 2022, residents of the region put forward 13,691 initiatives (22 percent of total initiatives), and in the 1st season of 2023, 9,593 (17 percent) initiatives.

Figure 5.

It should be noted that the number of projects submitted by citizens to the "Initiative Budget" is decreasing from season to season. In 2021, the first season of the project passed with 41 thousand initiatives (the project consisted of one season that year). The number of offers was about 70,000 in the 1st season of 2022, 62,000 in the 2nd season, 56,000 in the 1st season of 2023, and 49,000 in the 2nd season. At the moment, offers for the 2nd season of 2023 have covered almost all neighborhoods across the country.

Tashabbusli budjet jarayonining 2023 yil 1-mavsumi doirasida kelib tushgan loyihalar yuzasidan hududlar va yo'nalishlar kesimida ma'lumot

16 fevral soat 10-00 holatiga

T/r	Hudud nomi	Jami loyihalar	shundan						
			Umumta'lim maktablarini ta'mirlash va jihozlash	Ichki yo'llarni ta'mirlash	Ichimlik suvi ta'minoti	Ko'cha chiroqlarini o'rnatish	Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarini ta'mirlash va jihozlash	Tibbiyot tashkilotlarini ta'mirlash va jihozlash	Boshqalar
	Jami	27 184	5 272	7 806	1 131	2 796	2 237	1 286	6 656
1	Surxondaryo viloyati	3 445	775	789	210	519	381	162	609
2	Toshkent shahri	3 360	557	455	93	173	473	299	1 310
3	Qashqadaryo viloyati	3 075	449	1 259	158	361	105	130	613
4	Buxoro viloyati	2 385	330	687	109	271	127	104	757
5	Namangan viloyati	2 295	758	417	45	92	441	140	402
6	Xorazm viloyati	2 169	390	753	71	300	129	74	452
7	Toshkent viloyati	1 726	280	673	82	267	56	35	333
8	Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi	1 716	247	487	104	206	62	31	579
9	Andijon viloyati	1 521	253	724	56	164	63	31	230
10	Farg'ona viloyati	1 253	214	445	59	160	97	50	228
11	Jizzax viloyati	1 189	297	320	33	63	65	28	383
12	Samarqand viloyati	1 187	269	419	36	124	70	70	199
13	Navoiy viloyati	975	273	169	17	36	92	102	286
14	Sirdaryo viloyati	888	180	209	58	60	76	30	275

Ташаббусли бюджет 2023 йил 2- мавсум

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Figure 6.

In the 2nd season of 2023, a total of 12,279 projects were received in the Surkhandarya region, 5,977 were shortlisted, and as a result, 76 projects won with 1,704 votes (Fig. 6).

Figure 7.

In the 2nd season of 2023, in connection with the implementation of a total of 76 winning projects in the Surkhandarya region, 22 projects are under construction and 54 projects have been completed (Fig. 7).

Figure 8.

The winning projects were subjected to public scrutiny, and if we analyze the example of Surkhandarya, 82% were found to be positive and 18% were found to be satisfactory (Fig. 7). For the initiative budget process, 107,305,852,217 soums have been allocated to the Surkhandarya region from the total 1,424,373,806,304 soums for the 2nd season of 2023.

CONCLUSION

As a result of the research, it can be concluded that in order to effectively control the implementation of the budget, the budget formation process, as well as the stages of spending, should be as transparent as possible and should be controlled by the public. As a result, the funds of the republican budget and local budgets should be developed in more detail in all directions, and even the payment of the minimum amount should be carried out openly. For this, budget implementation should be detailed, open and understandable to the public as much as possible. Local executive bodies, in turn, learn to see the needs of the population not in the form of complaints or in the form of complaints, but in the form of reasonable and reasonable proposals. In the initiative budget process, an active community is formed that is ready to work in cooperation and solve complex tasks, has the authority to independently create projects, identify, form and develop new resources for the development of the region.

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